

PROJECT MANAGER LEADERSHIP STYLE, TEAMWORK, PROJECT CHARACTERISTICS AND PERFORMANCE OF WATER PROJECTS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: The overall objective of this study was to determine the relationship between project manager's leadership style, teamwork, project characteristics and their impact on project performance in water sector projects in Nigeria. To achieve the objective, hypothesis were formulated namely there is no significant relationship between project manager's leadership style and project performance; there is no significant relationship between project manager's leadership style and teamwork; there is no significant relationship between teamwork and project performance; the relationship between project manager's leadership style and project performance is not intervened by teamwork; the relationship between project manager's leadership style and project performance is not moderated by project characteristics; and the joint effect of project manager's leadership style, project characteristics and teamwork on project performance is not significant. Through the use of positivist research paradigm and descriptive cross-sectional research design, primary data was collected from project managers and project team members involved in water projects in the country while secondary data was collected from project files. Project performance was evaluated in terms of Time Performance Index (TPI) and Cost Performance Index (CPI). The study findings are that there is statistically significant relationship between project manager's leadership style and project time performance; there is a statistically significant positive relationship between project manager's leadership style and teamwork; there is a statistically significant relationship between teamwork and project time performance; the relationship between project manager's leadership style and project time performance is mediated by teamwork; and moderated by project complexity; and there is a statistically significant combined effect on the relationship between project manager's leadership style, teamwork, project characteristics and project time performance. However, no statistically significant relationship was found between project manager's leadership style and project cost performance. Although the study findings confirm existence of a statistically significant relationship between project manager's leadership style and project time performance, the findings indicate that the relationship was not direct as it was mediated by teamwork. In addition, the study has shown the moderating role of project characteristics in the relationship between project manager's leadership style and project time performance. The study findings have also identified the importance of transformational leadership style and teamwork in enhancing performance of water projects in Nigeria. This implies that clients should consider leadership style and team building capabilities of project managers before allocating them projects. Further, with leadership being critical, there is need for curricular review as a way of ensuring that graduates have the right mix of technical and leadership skills necessary for successful project execution.

Keywords: Teamwork, Leadership Style, Project Manager, Water projects.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Globally, there has been a significant increase in the number of project activities (Winter & Zzepanek, 2008). The British Standard (BS 6079:2000) defines a project as a unique set of co-ordinated activities, with definite starting and finishing point, undertaken by an individual or organization to meet specific performance objectives within defined schedule, cost and performance parameters. On the other hand, the Project Management Institute (PMI) (2004) notes that a project is a temporary endeavour undertaken to create a unique product, service or results. Due to increased emphasis on projects and the fact that the utility of a project depends upon successful project completion, project management field of study has emerged as a distinct discipline from general management (Cleland & Ireland, 2002). Chase, et al., (2001) defines project management as the process of planning, directing, and controlling resources in order to ensure high level of project performance which is normally expressed in terms of time, cost, and quality and stakeholder satisfaction perspectives. With the objective of enhancing project performance, the PMI has a Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK) guide which documents processes, knowledge areas and best practices applicable in most projects. In the current PMBOK, five basic process groups and ten knowledge areas are documented with issues related to two of the areas namely time and cost management being the subject of this study (PMI, 2013).

Despite the importance and emphasis on projects, the end results for most projects have not been exciting with majority of projects across different countries, industries and sectors registering poor performance. Indeed, a review of extant literature shows that time and cost over-runs have become the norm rather than an exception (Jugdev & Muller 2005; Kibuchi, 2012). Consequently, there has been increased number of litigations, wastage of resources, negative reputation of clients and professionals involved in unsuccessful projects as well as lack of envisioned product, service or change (Aibinu & Jagboro, 2002; Jugdev & Muller, 2005).

1.2 Research Problem

One of the most significant trends in the world has been the increasing amount of project activities across different sectors and industries (Winter & Szczepanek, 2008). With the utility of a project being dependent upon successful completion, the search for ways of enhancing project performance has been on for several years (Al-Hejji, 2006) which has led to identification of critical success factors. Despite this, poor project performance seems to be a universal phenomenon in construction projects (Talukhaba, 1999; Assaf & Al-Hejji, 2006; 11 Frimpong, et al., 2003, Gichunge, 2000). With leadership having been recognised as a key success factor in general management (Dulewicz & Higgs, 2005; Zaccaro, et al., 2001) and the fact that leadership style is positively related to teamwork in terms of team communication, collaboration and cohesiveness (Zaccaro, et al., 2001; Wang, et al., 2005), it would be expected that project manager's leadership style should influence teamwork and project performance. In addition, based on contingency theory it is expected that project characteristics would influence leadership style adopted within a project. In Nigeria, investments in water and sanitation projects are huge. For instance, the total development expenditure on water supplies and related services increased from NShs 20.5 billion in 2012/13 to NShs 44.5 billion in 2013/14 financial year (NNBS, 2014).

1.3 Research Objectives

The overall objective of this study was to study and examine the project manager's leadership style, teamwork, project characteristics and their subsequent impact on project performance in water sector projects in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. Study and examine the current Project Manager's leadership style, teamwork and projects characteristics within water sector projects in Nigeria.
2. Establish the relationship between Projects Manager's LS, T & PC and their impact on the project performance of water sector projects in Nigeria.
3. Propose a set of solutions to overcome the shortcoming of the Project Manager's LS, T & PC impact on the performance of water sector projects in Nigeria.

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1.4 Research Questions

The research question include the follows bellows:

- Q1: During the project execution, does the project manager talked about his/her most important values and beliefs and the project manager specified the importance of having a strong sense of purpose during the project execution?
- Q2: Does the project manager provided the project team members with assistance in exchange for their efforts?
- Q3: Does the project manager made it clear what each project member was to receive once the project performance goals are achieved?
- Q4: During the project execution, does the project manager focused attention on irregularities, mistakes, exceptions and deviations from standards?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

To analyse the data, the following hypotheses were tested:

- H1a: There is significance relationship between PM's leadership style and the projects performance of water projects in Nigeria.
- H1b: Is no significant relationship between PM's leadership style and the projects performance of water projects in Nigeria?
- H2a: There is significance relationship between teamwork and peoples of water projects in Nigeria.
- H2b: There is no significance relationship between teamwork and peoples of water projects in Nigeria.
- H3a: There is significance relationship between projects characteristics and peoples of water projects in Nigeria.
- H3b: There is no significant relationship between PC a people of water projects in Nigeria.
- H4a: There is significant relationship between projects managers LS, T and PC to people of water project in Nigeria.

1.6 The Significance of the Research

The water sector plays an important role in the social-economic development of the country. Thus, the results of this study will be useful to various stakeholders and will make several contributions. For the government, development partners, project managers, consultants, contractors and clients in the water sector, the study has clarified the relationship between project manager's leadership style, teamwork, project characteristics and project performance. Through this, project managers are expected to adopt appropriate leadership style which will enhance project performance in the water sector. With enhanced project performance in the water sector, the study findings will result in values for money and hence reduce wastage of public funds through reduction of time and cost over-runs. This will enable the government to channel available resources to other sectors of the economy. In addition, the study findings are expected to spur social economic development in the country through provision of affordable and sustainable water services to industries and the citizens. Further, completion of sanitation projects on time and within budget will support government effort of addressing health and hygiene issues.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter examines both conceptual and empirical literature on leadership style, teamwork, project characteristics and project performance. Theoretical and conceptual framework has also been covered in this chapter.

2.2 Theoretical Foundation

Several theories exist that explains the relationship between leadership style, teamwork, project characteristics and project performance. These theories include visionary leadership theory, Resource Based View (RBV) theory, contingency theory, stakeholder theory and agency theory. A summary of these theories and their implications to this study are discussed in the sections that follow.

2.2.1 Visionary Leadership Theory

The literature on leadership is vast and this has resulted in several definitions with Higgs, (2003) defining leadership as a dynamic process in which one individual influences others to contribute to the achievement of the group tasks. Although there is no universal definition, one key aspect is that leadership is a process and hence time is needed for a leader to influence subordinates in the desired way. Leaders influence followers by communicating ideas, creating acceptance of the ideas, motivating them to support and implement the ideas. While leadership is part of a manager's job, leaders always have the ability to influence will but managers may not. Leaders influence followers differently and hence leader's exhibit a combination of traits, skills and behaviours which have resulted in different schools of thought or different leadership styles (Dulewicz & Higgs, 2005; Turner & Muller, 2005; Higgs, 2003).

Over the past decade, there have been six schools of leadership theory namely the trait, behavioural, contingency, visionary, and emotional and competency school (Turner & Muller, 2005). The trait theory was most prevalent up-to 1940 and the key idea behind the trait approach was that effective leaders have common characteristics and hence leaders are born and not made (Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1991; Turner & Muller, 2005).

2.2.2 Resource Based View Theory (RBV)

The theoretical foundation of RBV dates back Penrose's view of an organization as a pool of resources and articulation of the same by Wernerfelt in 2005 Ray, et al., 2004; The RBV consider the resources of a firm as being fundamental determinants of competitive advantage and performance. Whereas resources wrong can be categorized in different ways, for instance tangible and intangible, tangible resources facilitate execution of business process while the intangible resources are the ones that might result in competitive advantage by allowing organizations to incorporate unique and valuable practices (Ray, et al., 2004).

The RBV is based on two assumptions of resources being heterogeneously distributed across organizations and the non-transferability of productive resources from one organization to another without incurring cost. Thus, given the two assumptions, RBV holds that only an intangible resource that is valuable, rare, hard to imitate and without strategically equivalent substitutes is critical in sustaining a firm's competitiveness (Ray, et al., 2004).

2.2.3 Contingency Theory

The history of contingency theory can be traced back to the late 1950, in which Woodward (1958) argued that technologies determine differences in organizational features such as span of control, level of centralization of authority and formalization of rules and procedures. Thereafter, Burns and Stalker (1961) introduced the notion of mechanistic and organic organizations in which they proposed the use of organic organizations in turbulent environments. In addition, Lawrence and Lorsch (1967) investigated on how different rates of change can impact on organizations ability to cope. Although the theory was initially concerned with organization's structural issues, other aspects have been incorporated for instance Fiedler (1967) focused on leadership aspects while Doty and Delery (1996) have concentrated on human resource related issues.

2.3 Agency Theory

The agency theory is concerned with the relationship between the principal and the agent, in which the principal delegates work to the agent, who then in turn performs the work on behalf of the principal (Eisenhardt, 1989). In the construction industry, the relationship between the project owner and the contractor creates a principal-agent relationship in which the

principal (project owner) depends on the agent (contractor) to achieve the project objectives. However, within projects, the principal–agent relationship is complicated by the fact that the principal and the agent also delegate their duties to their respective project managers. This creates multiple relationships in which several participants with divergent interest are expected to work together to achieve project goal (Turner and Muller, 2004).

2.4. Leadership and Project Performance

Kissi, et al., (2013) examined the impact of portfolio manager’s transformational leadership style on project performance through administration of questionnaires to 350 project managers in the United Kingdom (UK). Using data from 112 completed responses, the study found that transformational leadership behavior of portfolio managers was positively related to project performance. The results were consistent with Waldman and Atwater (1994) study who found that transformational leadership of higher level managers positively influenced project outcomes (quality, cost, time and stakeholders satisfaction). In addition, innovation championing and existence of a climate for innovation were found to intervene on the relationship between transformational leadership and project performance. However, the study was based on one organization which limited generalizability of the results.

2.4.1 Leadership, Teamwork and Project Performance

Wang, et al., (2005) investigated the impact of charismatic leadership style on team cohesiveness and performance of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) project through administration of 300 questionnaires to project team members in Taiwan. Based on 106 returned questionnaires, they found a significant correlation between leadership style of ERP project manager and level of team cohesiveness. In addition, the study found a positive correlation between team cohesiveness and project performance. The results were consistent with those of Cheung, et al., (2001) findings that charismatic leadership has enormous effect on team members’ behaviour and efforts as well as those of Thite (2000) who found a correlation between charismatic leadership and project performance.

2.5 Summary of Empirical Studies and Research Gaps

An analysis of empirical literature on the relationship between leadership style, teamwork, project characteristics and project performance was undertaken and a number of research gaps were identified. These gaps include lack of consensus on which leadership style would enhance the likelihood of a project being successful. Secondly, the intervening role of teamwork on the relationship between project manager’s leadership style and project performance is not clear. Thirdly, there is lack of consensus on the effect of project characteristics such as size and complexity on the relationship between project manager’s leadership style and project performance.

2.6 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework was adopted for this study from a previous study.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the research methodology and details the research philosophy, the research design, the study population and sample, data collection methods, reliability and validity of the measurement instruments, operationalization of the study variables and data analysis.

3.2 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy refers to the fundamental belief about the way in which data about a phenomenon should be gathered, analysed and used. Within a continuum, two research philosophies exist namely phenomenological/naturalistic and positivistic paradigm. The two paradigms can be distinguished based on four axioms namely views about reality, cause and effect relationships, views about knowledge and truth, and relationship between investigator and inquiry (Mugenda, 2008).

3.3 Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional research design. As noted by Churchill and Iacobucci (2002), descriptive studies are structured with clearly stated hypotheses or investigative questions and serve a variety of research objectives including description of phenomena or characteristics of certain groups, estimation or prediction of the proportion of population with certain characteristics and determination of association among different variables.

3.4 Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised of water and sanitation projects undertaken by WSBs and WSPs and which were completed in the last four years (2011 to 2014) across the country. Although 2014 water projects would have facilitated faster recall of what transpired during project execution and also easy access to project team members, the number of projects was not adequate to facilitate testing of research hypothesis and hence the period of study was extended to four years.

3.5 Data Collection

The study made use of secondary and primary data and in respect to each project, secondary data used in the study comprised of budgeted project cost, actual project cost at the time of completion, budgeted project duration and actual project duration. Secondary data was collected from WSB's license achievement reports and project files that were available at WSB and WSP offices. Details of consultants and contractors were also collected at the time of collecting secondary data in order to facilitate administration of questionnaires. To facilitate secondary data collection, a secondary data collection form was used.

3.6 Validity and Reliability

Validity refers to the extent with which the instrument being used is measuring the concept set out to measure. For validity, the instrument was first subjected to an expert evaluation in which its adequacy was assessed given the study objectives. In addition, the questionnaire was subjected to a pilot survey to ensure clarity and understand ability of the survey instruments. Results of the expert evaluation and pilot survey were used to update the study instruments. A similar approach was used by other research such as Gichunge (2000) and Kibuchi (2012).

3.7 Operationalization of Study Variables

Operationalization of variables entailed development of an operational definition to facilitate measurement of the study variables. The independent variable; leadership style was operationalized into two variables namely transformational and transactional leadership styles. These two leadership styles were further operationalized in accordance with the latest version of the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) 5x-short. Consequently, transformational leadership had four subscales namely idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration while transactional leadership was operationalized into three subscales namely contingency reward, MBEA and MBEP.

3.8 Data Analysis

To prepare data for analysis, completed questionnaires were checked for consistency, coded and data entered into a database. For each project, completeness of data was based on availability of secondary data, receipt of project manager's questionnaire and at least a questionnaire from one of the project team members. Since the unit of analysis was project, multiple responses for a given project were consolidated through computation of mean rating for each of the Likert scale items.

3.9 Data Collection Instrument

In the quantitative analysis, the study we will use the rating scale instrument which is composed of a set of 5 categories designed to obtain information for the quantitative analysis. The type of rating scale is Likert scale which is widely used in research that employs questionnaires for measuring many scientific and social studies and in this study the Likert scale will be used mainly to identify the impact of factors that affecting the performance of managers. The five categories of Likert scale that will be used for the questionnaire of this study is (Strongly agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly disagree). Likert scale is important to this study because it is a bipolar scaling method, it means the measuring of respondent opinions either positive or negative response to the questions distributed for the study population.

3.10 The type of Data

The type of data obtained from the quantitative research is numerical tables containing data in the form statistical numbers like the mean value and standard deviation factor, reliability factor, validity, frequencies, and the mode numbers. The collected in this study is associated with the characteristics of the project manager's leadership style and performance. The study will utilize both secondary and primary data to make the necessary recommendations and concluding the accurate results. The secondary data will be based on different literatures associated with this subject. The secondary data will be collected from published journal about the topic.

3.11 The Analysis Software

The study will use Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) to make the statistical analysis from the collected data. SPSS Statistics is a software package used for statistical analysis, the software is used for survey authoring and deployment (IBM SPSS Data Collection), data mining, text analytics, and collaboration and deployment (batch and automated scoring services).

3.12 Chapter Summary

This chapter illustrated and showed the main research techniques and methodologies that will be applied in the study and specified three types of variables (dependent, moderate, and independent) which will be examined and evaluated in the study.

4. DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION

4.1 Introduction

This chapter covers the response rate, respondent's profile, diagnostics tests, projects characteristics and descriptive statistics of key study variable. In addition, relationship among variables, hypothesis testing and discussions of findings are presented. This chapter starts with presentation and analysis and of the background information about the respondents, and thereafter it presents and analyse data basing on the specific objectives of the study which were to identify the project manager leadership style, teamwork, project characteristics and performance of water project in Nigeria.

4.2 Response Rate

Out of the targeted 180 respondents, complete data (primary and secondary) was received for 180 giving a response rate of 100 percent. This response rate was considered good for further analysis based on Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) and Saunders et al., (2007) assertion that a response rate of 50 percent is adequate, 60 percent is good while a responses rate of 70 percent is very good. In addition, this response rate was within the range of responses rate for similar researches.

4.2.1 Demographic Characteristic of the Respondents

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are shown in table and chart below. The gender distribution of the respondents was quite even, with (68.3%) male respondents and (31.7%) female respondents. The male respondents carried the highest number of percentage in the questionnaire which means out of 180 questions distribute male gender is the top on given their feedback (Table 1).

Table 1: Gender Respondent

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Male	123	68.0	68.3
	Female	57	31.5	31.7
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

Figure 2: Respondent Gender

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are shown in table and chart below. The Age distribution of the respondents was quite even, 19 – 20 (16.1%), 21 -24 (36.1%), 25 – 30 (16.1%) while 31 and above twenty percentage (31.7%). 21 – 30 respondents carried the highest number of percentage in the questionnaire. (Table 2).

Table 2: Respondent's age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	19 - 20	29	16.0	16.1
	21 - 24	65	35.9	36.1
	25 - 30	29	16.0	16.1
	31 and Above	57	31.5	31.7
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

Figure 3: Respondent Age

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are shown in table and chart below. The working experience of the respondents was quite even, 0 – 1 year (32.2%), 2 – 3 years (36.1%), and 4 – 5 years (31.7%). 2 – 3 years respondents carried the highest number of percentage in the questionnaire. (Table 3).

Table 3: Respondents working experience

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	0 – 1 years	58	32.0	32.2
	2 – 3 years	65	35.9	36.1
	4 – 5 years	57	31.5	31.7
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

Figure 4: Respondents working experience

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (1-14), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are shown in table and chart below. The qualification of the respondents was quite even, Diploma (30.2%), Bachelor Degree (35.9%), and Master’s Degree (16.0%), and PhD Degree (15.5%). Bachelor Degree respondents carried the highest number of percentage in the questionnaire. (Table 4).

Table 4: Respondent’s Qualification

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Diploma	58	32.0	32.2
	Bachelor Degree	65	35.9	36.1
	Master Degree	29	16.0	16.1
	PhD Degree	28	15.5	15.6
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

Figure 5: Respondents Qualification

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are shown in table and chart below. The project compare at the organization of the respondents was quite even, low (35.9%), medium (47.5%) and high (16.0%). Medium respondents carried the highest number of percentage in the questionnaire. (Table 5).

Table 5: Compared to other projects that your organization has undertaken in the past, kindly rate the project complexity

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Low	65	35.9	36.1
	Medium	86	47.5	47.8
	High	29	16.0	16.1
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

Figure 6: Respondent's project compare

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are shown in table and chart below. The organization project compare of the respondents was quite even, Greenfield (16.0%), Renovation (51.9%), and Expansion (31.5%). Renovation respondents carried the highest number of percentage in the questionnaire. (Table 6).

Table 6: For the above mentioned project, kindly specify the project type/initial site condition

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Greenfield	29	16.0	16.1
	Renovation	94	51.9	52.2
	Expansion	57	31.5	31.7
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are shown in table and chart below. The classification of the contract of the respondents was quite even, local (51.4%), and international (48.1%). Local respondents carried the highest number of percentage in the questionnaire. (Table 7).

Table 7: Classification of the main contractor

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Local	93	51.4	51.7
	International	87	48.1	48.3
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

4.3 Reliability Analysis

Reliability is defined as the consistency of measures of a variable. Table shows the result of reliability test of this research. According to Neuman (2006), reliability of a research measured to the extent that the measures are free from error, procedures are stable, and coefficients are consistent.

According to Kline (2014), the acceptable value of alpha in reliability analysis is 0.8 in the case of intelligence tests, and the acceptable value of alpha in reliability analysis is 0.7 in the case of ability tests (Table 8).

Table 8: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.413	23

The Scales were developed and applied in this study to hypothesize 23 items. These scales were extracted from a comprehensive review of theoretical and empirical literature.

4.4 Frequencies

The Table 9 of frequency on this item shows that highest percentage of this question (51.9%). This indicates that the employees that respondents to this question choose “Disagree” which seen to be the highest percentage.

Table 9: Project team members avoided drifting from the topic during discussions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Disagree	94	51.9	52.2
	Agree	57	31.5	31.7
	Strongly Agree	29	16.0	16.1
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

The Table 10 of frequency on this item shows that highest percentage of this question is (35.9%). This indicates that the employees that respondents to this question choose “Agree” which seen to be the highest percentage.

Table 10: Project team members responded to each other positively during discussions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Disagree	29	16.0	16.1
	Neutral Agree	29	16.0	16.1
	Agree	65	35.9	36.1
	Strongly Agree	57	31.5	31.7
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

The Table 11 of frequency on this item shows that highest percentage of this question is (51.9%). This indicates that the employees that respondents to this question choose “Neutral Agree” which seen to be the highest percentage.

Table 11: Project team members did not show a defensive or mistrustful attitude during discussions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Neutral Agree	94	51.9	52.2
	Agree	29	16.0	16.1
	Strongly Agree	57	31.5	31.7
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (1-14), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

The Table 12 of frequency on this item shows that highest percentage of this question is (51.4%). This indicates that the employees that respondents to this question choose “Agree” which seen to be the highest percentage.

Table 12: Project team members discussed problem-solving methods and collaborated with others to address them

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Disagree	58	32.0	32.2
	Neutral Agree	29	16.0	16.1
	Agree	93	51.4	51.7
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

The Table 13 of frequency on this item shows that highest percentage of this question is (48.1%). This indicates that the employees that respondents to this question choose “Agree” which seen to be the highest percentage.

Table 13: Every project team member felt responsible for maintaining and protecting the project

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Disagree	65	35.9	36.1
	Neutral Agree	28	15.5	15.6
	Agree	87	48.1	48.3
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

The Table 14 of frequency on this item shows that highest percentage of this question is (90.1%). This indicates that the employees that respondents to this question choose “neutral Agree” which seen to be the highest percentage.

Table 14: Project team members listened to each other to clarify problems/issues

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Disagree	7	3.9	3.9
	Neutral Agree	163	90.1	90.6
	Agree	4	2.2	2.2
	Strongly Agree	6	3.3	3.3
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

The Table 15 of frequency on this item shows that highest percentage of this question is (54.1%). This indicates that the employees that respondents to this question choose “Strongly Agree” which seen to be the highest percentage.

Table 15: Project team members were strongly attached to the project and project team members felt proud to be part of the project

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Neutral Agree	2	1.1	1.1
	Agree	80	44.2	44.4
	Strongly Agree	98	54.1	54.4
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (1-14), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

The Table 16 of frequency on this item shows that highest percentage of this question is (70.7%). This indicates that the employees that respondents to this question choose “Yes” which seen to be the highest percentage.

Table 16: Should project team members avoided drifting from the topic during discussions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Yes	128	70.7	71.1
	No	1	.6	.6
	No Idea	51	28.2	28.3
	Total	180	99.4	100.0
Missing	System	1	.6	
Total		181	100.0	

The Table of frequency on this item shows that highest percentage of this question is (45.3%). This indicates that the employees that respondents to this question choose “No” which seen to be the highest percentage.

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